

AGRICULTURAL PRACTICES, ENERGY CONSUMPTION AND CO_2 EMISSION IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study explored how agriculture and energy contribute to reducing carbon dioxide (CO_2) emissions in Nigeria by adopting the secondary time-series data from 2019 to 2024 and utilized the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) to analyze the short and long run relationships between energy use, agricultural output and CO_2 emissions in Nigeria. Findings revealed that agriculture is a major contributor in reducing greenhouse gas emissions in Nigeria. On a contrary, energy consumption increases CO_2 emissions which is an indication of Nigeria's dependence on fossil fuels consumption. With these outcomes, agricultural outputs reduce the severity of environmental degradation, while the energy sector demands immediate reforms towards renewable and cleaner sources. This study recommended that sustainable agricultural practices coupled with investments in renewable energy should be encouraged so as to foster the achievements of the expected sustainable goals in Nigeria.

Keywords: *Agricultural Practices, Energy, CO_2 Emission, Environmental sustainability, fossil fuel.*

JEL Code: *C13, Q10, Q22, Q42*

1. INTRODUCTION

The environmental issues involved with carbon-dioxide emission has become a global concern due to its implications on climate change, human health and the achievement of sustainable development. Nigeria, just like other developing economies, is faced with the dual challenge of accomplishing rapid economic growth while reducing environmental degradation. As the country's main energy source, fossil fuels have continued to have a significant contributor to its CO_2 emissions. The enormous dependency on fossil fuels in many sectors of the economy has led to a high level of CO_2 emissions (Tunde et al., 2022). Concurrently, Agriculture plays a major role in Nigeria's economy by contributing massively to employment, food security and gross domestic product. However, the impacts of these agricultural practices on the

environment can be both positive and negative. Modernized and sustainable agricultural practices help absorb carbon and reduce emissions, whereas traditional and subsistence methods can worsen environmental problems. This dual role of agriculture and the heavy reliance on fossil-fuel energy highlights the importance of examining how these sectors contribute to the reduction of CO_2 emissions in Nigeria (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC,2014)

Despite the various environmental initiatives, the rising levels of greenhouse gas emissions still persist in Nigeria which may be attributed primarily to unclean energy usage and inefficient agricultural practices. In Nigeria, CO_2 emissions from non-renewable energy production (oil, coal, and gas) and agricultural activities (deforestation, burning of biomass and usage of fertilizers), offer major environmental hazards (Dansofo et al., 2024). The potentials of agricultural practices for emission reduction have not been adequately utilized while environmental degradation has been intensified due to the persistent dependence on fossil fuels. The past research has offered diverse viewpoints on the importance of agriculture and energy in the reduction of CO_2 emissions in Nigeria and other nations. Most of the studies demonstrates a favorable association between agricultural, energy and CO_2 emissions Wang et al. (2023); Ghimire et al. (2023); Khan et al. (2023); Edoja et al. (2016), notably in Nigeria. This indicates that an increase in agriculture or energy leads to an increase in CO_2 emissions. Although various research has explored the link between agriculture, energy and CO_2 emissions, major gaps remain. Most empirical studies within Nigeria (Edoja et al., 2016; Ghimire et al., 2023)

In spite of an extensive literature on the agriculture–energy–emissions nexus, significant gaps remain in the Nigerian context. Most studies examine agriculture and energy in isolation, overlooked the mitigation role of sustainable agriculture, ignore technological and renewable energy transitions, and rely on outdated datasets (Talukder et Al., 2021; Mensah et al., 2018; Ozca & Strauss 2016; Zhang & Cheng, 2009). Furthermore, few studies integrate macroeconomic variables such as urbanization and trade into a unified empirical framework or apply ARDL methodologies tailored to short-span but not on recent datasets. The interaction between agricultural sustainability, renewable energy adoption, and CO_2 emissions remains insufficiently explored. This study fills these gaps by providing updated evidence on the joint effects of agricultural output and energy consumption on CO_2 emissions in Nigeria, using recent data (2019–2024) and an ARDL approach that captures both short-run and long-run dynamics.

In addition, the role of novel agricultural approaches such as vertical agriculture (The Guardian, 2025) has been investigated worldwide, but requires empirical proof within the agricultural industry of Nigeria. Also, the linkages between agricultural sustainability, the adoption of renewable energy and the reduction of emissions remain unexplored, as indicated by Rafiq et al. (2016) and Regmi et al. (2024).

This study aims to fill the gap in knowledge on the specific impacts of agriculture and energy-related activities on Nigeria’s capacity to lower greenhouse gas emissions.

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1.1 Theoretical Literature

Energy is a resource created, utilized and traded within an economic system, and can be referred to as the capacity to perform a task or work (Smil, 2017). It comprises of primary resources such as crude oil, coal, natural gas, solar radiation, and wind, as well as secondary energy products including gasoline, diesel, liquefied natural gas (LNG), and electricity, which can be converted into productive activities (IEA, 2022). As a good determinant of the modern

industrial economy, energy has been seen as a central to everyday human activities such as cooking, transportation, lighting, and heating. Energy sources take multiple forms of wind, fossil fuels, solar, geothermal, and nuclear with distinct characteristics, environmental implications, and economic costs (Sovacool, 2019). Nigeria can be referred to as the energy giant of Africa, and services as one of the continent's largest producers of crude oil and holding, together with Libya, nearly two-thirds of Africa's proven crude reserves. Nigeria is also ranked second only to Algeria in natural gas reserves in Africa (OPEC, 2023). As a commercial commodity, energy is traded from surplus or the producing nations to the countries with deficits, and countries such as Nigeria leverage abundant natural resources to meet domestic demand while supporting export markets (Akinyemi et al., 2021).

According to the International Energy Agency (IEA), (2022), the biggest energy sources in Nigeria in 2022 are: biofuels and waste, which constitute about 43.4% of the overall energy supply, oil also represents 32.2% of the entire energy supply. Biofuels are largely gotten from plants and waste items such as industrial waste and home wastes. These are burnt to create heat and electricity and, although they can be good for the climate and the general environment, the impact varies considerably depending on the fuel source and how it was utilized. Biofuels are employed in much of the energy system. They are used to generate power, as an alternative for oil-based fuels in transport, to heat buildings or to supply heat for industrial operations. Oil-based fuels are vital to the modern world. Millions of automobiles, aircraft, etc. drive, yet the combustion of these oil-based fuels is a primary source of CO_2 emissions unlike the renewable sources of energy.

The renewable energy sources are generally a low or zero carbon footprint and may be utilized to generate power, heat buildings and more. In general, renewable energy sources create substantially fewer emissions than fossil fuels (Ehrlich et al, 2020). The fundamental motive to replace fossil fuels with renewable energy sources is to stop or reduce climate change, which is widely accepted to be driven largely by greenhouse gas emissions. Nigeria is currently researching renewable energy possibilities to diversify her energy mix and lessen dependency on non-renewable sources. 35 There is no energy sources in Nigeria that is dominated by thermal energy generating sources (80%) and hydroelectric (20%). This energy mix has created a National Energy Transition Plan with ambitions to generate 30,000 MW of power from renewable sources and attain carbon neutrality in 2060. Renewable energy sources have a large potential to enhance and make a difference in low level access to power in Nigeria (Shaaban & Petinrin, 2014).

Non-renewable energy sources are resources that cannot be replenished after they are depleted. Four important sources of non-renewable energy are coal, oil, natural gas and nuclear energy. Nigeria is mostly non-renewable, dependent largely on fossil fuels such as oil and natural gas, thereby establishing one of the biggest crude oil producers in Africa (IEA, 2023). However, initiatives are being implemented to assure the development of renewable energy potentials in order to diversify the mix of energy and minimize dependency on non-renewable sources. Currently, thermal sources (80%) and hydroelectric (20%) dominate the mix of energy of the Nigeria system. Fossil fuels are non-renewable energy sources that derive from the remnants of plants and animals that died millions of years ago. They consist of carbon-rich deposits that derive from the buried remains of ancient animals. The type of fossil fuel develops based on the type of organic matter, the quantity of heat and pressure, and how long it has been buried (IEA, 2023).

The organic matter is burnt and turned into power or are processed into fuels for transport and heating. These fuels are utilized even more to create goods such as plastic and steel. The environmental implications of fossil fuel combustion include the release of the carbon

atmosphere that leads to global climate change. In Nigeria, fossil fuels are responsible for more than 80 % of anthropogenic carbon dioxide emissions, while more than 40 percent of carbon dioxide emissions (CO_2) connected to energy in the country occur from fossil fuel combustion, principally coal burning for power production (IEA, 2023). Fossil fuels are non-renewable energy sources that derive from the remnants of plants and animals that died millions of years ago.

Fossil fuels are formed from carbon-rich deposits derived from the buried remains of prehistoric plants and animals. The type of fossil fuel produced depends on the nature of the organic matter, the degree of heat and pressure applied, and the length of time the material remains buried (Speight, 2019). These fuels are used for power generation and refined into energy carriers such as gasoline, diesel, and heating fuels; they are also essential inputs for manufacturing products like plastics and steel (IEA, 2023).

2.1.2 The Concept of Agriculture and CO_2 Emissions

Agriculture can simply be referred to as the process of cultivating land to produce crops and raising animals in order to generate food and other things for people. It entails nurturing the land, employing the science of plants and implementing current production methods. According to agriculture remains the backbone of the Nigerian economy, providing the animation for majority of the Nigerians. It is acknowledged that agriculture is the cornerstone of emerging economies, notably in nations in Africa, where it contributes nearly 50% of total employment and life 36. (Osabohien et al., 2020).

However, the agricultural sector depends largely on favorable climates, for example, temperature, floods, rain and other aspects of the climate that affect agricultural productivity, food supply and basic products prices and finally destabilize economic performance (Kang et al., 2009; Magadza, 2000). In addition, Wisner et al. (2004) note that the vulnerability of agricultural productivity may not be determined by some environmental stress, such as climate change, but by the combination of societal capability to cope with environmental changes.

Subsistence Agriculture is the most commonly practiced type of agriculture in Nigeria: This involves raising crops for personal use. It supplies food for a community and is the major source of income for many Nigerians. It employs little quantities of cash and makes use of traditional tools. It also incorporates agricultural practices like mixed cropping and unimproved kinds of crops and animals raising which provides little or no surplus for sale. Subsistence agriculture helps in rural development and economic progress (Adegboye, 2017, Adebayo & Udoh, 2019).

Subsistence agriculture is Nigeria's most widespread form of agriculture, especially in rural regions. In this style of agriculture, people or families produce crops and raise earlier to feed themselves and their immediate neighborhood. Subsistence agriculture employs around two thirds of the entire workforce in Nigeria and offers a living for the bulk of the rural population that can represent almost three quarters of the population with resources from the country (AFDB, 2011). Subsistence agriculture, although it is typically regarded less startling than large-scale industrial agriculture, nonetheless contributes to CO_2 emissions largely via activities like as deforestation for land clearing, the use of traditional fertilizers and cow keeping. These activities produce methane, a powerful greenhouse gas, through their digestive processes; However, compared to intensive agriculture, subsistence agriculture generally has a lower general carbon footprint due to its lower scale and dependence on local resources, but the amount it produces depends on factors such as location, livestock management and agricultural practices.

2.2. Theoretical Review.

2.2.1. Environmental Kuznets Curve Theory

Environmental deterioration is a subject of concern in Nigeria, and this includes CO_2 emissions. As for this research, this hypothesis intends to investigate the link between economic growth and environmental quality. The environmental Kuznets curve raises an inverted link in the form of subsidy between environmental deterioration (pollution) and economic progress. The name of Kuznets was linked to the curve of Grossman and Krueger (1995), who observed their similarities with the Kuznets inverted relationship between economic expansion and environmental deterioration, such as CO_2 emissions. It is considered that environmental deterioration increases with economic expansion at the beginning, but subsequently reduces after reaching a particular income threshold. In the early stage of economic expansion, there is a rise in pollution and emissions owing to industrialization and dependency on non-renewable energy. However, as economic levels, environmental awareness, regulatory frameworks and technical breakthroughs improve, contribute to a reduction in pollution (Grossman and Krueger, 1995). The idea of the Kuznets environmental curve is based on three stages: the first stage is the preindustrial stage, when there are little economic development and a poor reduction in CO_2 emissions. In this phase, there are limited industrial activity and pollution levels, which indicates that there is little usage of fossil fuels and minimum environmental controls. At this early stage of industrialization, economic growth is associated to increasing pollution due to a rise in energy consumption, industrialization and agricultural expansion. During this period, agriculture and energy had minimal contribution to CO_2 emissions, hence there was no genuine worry for emissions, as they were naturally low. However, dependency on conventional agriculture and inefficient energy sources can lead to land degradation and deforestation.

The second stage is the stage of industrial expansion that comprises of strong economic growth and high CO_2 emissions. This age is distinguished by rapid industrialization, the growth in the use of fossil fuels and environmental irresponsibility. As industrialization, fossil fuel use and large-scale agriculture increases contribute to the growth in CO_2 emissions. Nigeria was in this period in the 1970s, followed by the oil surge. In this phase, agriculture and energy had a major part in the contribution to the growth in CO_2 emissions in Nigeria. During this period, the energy industry, centered by crude oil and natural gas, became the greatest CO_2 emitter in Nigeria, mostly from bear, oil extraction and electricity production. There was also a fast development of mechanized agriculture, which led to a rise in fertilizer emissions, deforestation and changes in land use. In addition, there was a rise in energy consumption due to the substantial dependency on fossil fuels for power and transport. The idea of the environmental Kuznets curve argues that Nigeria might now be in the industrial boom stage, when economic activities still contribute to environmental deterioration and industrial activity and dependency on fossil fuels remain high. However, improved rules and clean technology can begin to minimize these emissions.

The third stage is the post-industrial period, and is distinguished by sustainable growth and the decrease of CO_2 emissions. Here, as there is continual economic expansion, CO_2 emissions begin to decline thanks to renewable energy, technical breakthroughs and environmental legislation. At higher income levels, advancements and technology strategies provide sustainable economic expansion with a limited environmental effect (Grossman and Krueger, 1995). Many developed countries are at this stage, but Nigeria has not yet crossed the transition from the industrial boom stage and for change, Nigeria has to concentrate so that its agriculture and energy sector is more sustainable. It has to implement sustainable agricultural techniques such as agroforestry, organic agriculture, decrease in the use of pesticides and conservation

agriculture that will assist reduce emissions by boosting carbon storage in soils and reduce deforestation. In addition, efficient irrigation methods and reduced dependence on synthetic fertilizers can minimize methane emissions (CH_4) and nitrous oxide (N_2O); This will help in the reduction of emissions in Nigeria. In addition, the promotion of bioenergy (for example, biogas of agricultural waste) can provide an alternative to fossil fuels. For sustainable energy, change to renewable energy sources such as solar energy and biomass, wind and hydroelectric energy can help reduce fossil fuels and CO_2 emissions. Improving energy efficiency and introducing government policies that promote investments in green technology can also accelerate Nigeria's transition to the sustainable phase of the hypothesis of the environmental Kuznets curve.

2.2.2. Green Theory

Climate change has become a global serious concern with CO_2 emissions that plays a vital role in environmental deterioration. Green growth theory was founded on the concept that economic growth and environmental sustainability may go hand in hand. This hypothesis claims that investments in clean technologies, renewable energy and sustainable agriculture may increase long-term economic development while lowering carbon emissions (OECD, 2012). Green theory evolved to serve as a long-term solution to these environmental challenges created by industrialization, globalization and unsustainable economic activities. Challenges traditional economic and political systems that favours development over sustainability (Eckersley, 2004). Green philosophy promotes ecological integrity, sustainability and fairness for both people and non-human organisms (Barry and Eckersley, 2005). Green theory encourages equality in the creation of environmental policy and highlights that underprivileged people frequently suffer the worst portion of environmental deterioration (Dobson, 1998). In Nigeria, farmers in rural regions suffer from land degradation owing to climate change, while urban areas have air pollution of energy production and mobility. Unlike other theories that concentrate human demands on nature, green theory encourages a situation where humans and nature live successfully (Barry, 2012). This idea is matched with the need for cleaner energy sources such as solar energy and wind in Nigeria to minimize CO_2 emissions while assuring economic prosperity. In addition, green theory encourages global environmental governance.

Green Theory gives useful insights that relate to Nigeria, it is confronted with some criticism. Critics claim that green theory encourages idealism regarding practicality. Green theory is excessively utopian and lacks realistic answers for economic progress in underdeveloped nations such as Nigeria (Dyer, 2014). The theory is frequently criticized for disregarding economic reality. Some scholars contend that green theory underestimates the impact of economic development in poverty alleviation, particularly in nations wealthy in resources (Newell, 2019). In addition, green theory is criticized for not sufficiently addressing the economic and political constraints found in the implementation of environmental policies. Nigeria, for example, suffers from corruption, which makes green legislation difficult to execute (Akinola, 2023]. While Green Theory gives useful insights that relate to Nigeria, she confronts criticism. Critics claim that green theory encourages idealism regarding practicality. Green theory is excessively utopian and lacks realistic answers for economic progress in underdeveloped nations such as Nigeria (Dyer, 2014). The theory is frequently criticized for disregarding economic reality. Some scholars contend that green theory underestimates the impact of economic development in poverty alleviation, particularly in nations wealthy in resources (Newell, 2019). In addition, green theory is criticized for not sufficiently addressing the economic and political constraints found in the implementation of environmental policies. Nigeria, for example, suffers with corruption, which makes green legislation difficult to execute (Akinola, 2023). In order solve these difficulties, technical improvements, regulatory

reforms and international cooperation are needed. Expanding solar, wind and hydroelectric power can induce a reduction in dependency on fossil fuels in Nigeria.

2.2.3. Sustainable Development Theory

The 'sustainable development concept has been known for about two centuries, owing to the debate on how resources replenish slowly can sustain the fast-growing population. The concern on how the world's natural resources will continue to satisfy the fast-growing population was first debated in the early 18th century by Thomas Robert Malthus. Malthus in 1798 formulated a clear environmental principle that views population to continue to grow at a geometrical progression while the resources available will continue to grow at an arithmetic progression. Hence, it will reach a point where the growth in the resources available will not be enough to satisfy the needs of the growing population (Eblen & Eblen 1994; Dixon & Fallon 1989). Freeman (1973) is of the view that from the days of Malthus, Economists have failed to divert their attention towards the scarcity of resources and environmental effects of the utilisation of available resources on human health. Economists were mainly concerned with the efficient utilisation of available resources, thereby ignoring theories that could contribute to ensuring sustainable growth and technical progress until the emergence of the modern-day economists. The phrase 'sustainable development' was first used in 1980 at the World Conservation Strategy organised by the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) and the International Union for the Conservation of Nature (IUCN). It was first coined by examining the relevance of 'conservation' of resources to achieve great sustainable benefits to present and future generations (Eblen & Eblen 1994). During the 1980s the outcome of the World Conservation Strategy and the need to ensure sustainable growth prompted economists to look for ways to offer solutions to the questions asked by Malthus on how the slow replenishing of resources could be used to sustain the ever-increasing population; that is, whether the course of economic development can be sustainable or not.

Kahn (1995) described sustainable development into three pillars or perspectives, which are: economic sustainability, economic sustainability, social, and environmental sustainability viewed from a growth, resource allocation and consumption perspective with the assumption that natural resources are unlimited and a record of growth in the economy should be extended to the poor people in the country.

2.2.4, Agriculture–Environment Interaction theory: The theory from different author; rather, it is a synthesized conceptual framework drawn from Boserup's seminal 1965 work agricultural intensification model, ecological–economic linkages (Grossman & Krueger, 1995), and agro-ecological systems research (Tilman et al., 2001; Pretty, 2008). The theory recognizes that agriculture has a direct relationship with both carbon dioxide and energy usage which can be positive or negative depending on the type of agricultural productivity being practiced. This implies that that agriculture can either worsen or reduce environmental degradation depending on practices (Bulut, & Gökalp, 2022; Grossman & Krueger, 1995).

2.3 Empirical Review.

2.3.1 Empirical Review within Nigeria.

Wu et al., (2025) adopted a net emission measuring system to determine the effect of agricultural productivity on carbon emission in Anui in China in 2023. Findings demonstrate a positive special correlation of carbon emission of agricultural productivity. The study recommends that political initiatives that focus on carbon dioxide sustainable agricultural development from accurate policy.

Edoja et al., (2024) investigated the impacts of energy consumption, Agricultural trade, and productivity on CO_2 emissions using quantile regression using time series data from 1960-2021. The research indicates that there is a beneficial influence of agricultural raw materials imports (AGRIMs) and exports on carbon footprints. In addition, the influence of energy consumption on CO_2 emissions vary across different quantiles, so implying that policy interventions should incorporate these differences to successfully reduce emissions.

Ju et al., (2023) studied the link between energy usage, agricultural output, and climate change in Nigeria from 1990 to 2017. The result from the Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) Model and Granger Causality tests applied suggested that an increase in energy consumption leads to increased CO_2 emissions, while an increase in agricultural output contributes to a reduction in CO_2 emissions. The research indicates that boosting energy efficiency and sustainable agriculture techniques will help lower CO_2 emissions in Nigeria. Wang et al., (2023) carried out this study to assess if renewable energy and agriculture may assist reduce CO_2 emissions for selected sub-Saharan African (SSA) nations including Nigeria. Employing the differentiated-generalized technique of moments, it was established that the consumption of renewable energy can reduce CO_2 emissions while Agriculture increases them. The study provides policy implications for enhancing renewable energy consumption and green agricultural growth to promote sustainable development in Sub-Saharan African (SSA) nations.

Dauda et al. (2023) examined the impacts of governance (corruption) and agricultural output on CO_2 emissions in 20 African nations, including Nigeria, from 1990-2019. The findings from the fixed effect model and panel dynamic ordinary least squares (PDOLS) demonstrate that renewable energy usage mitigates CO_2 emissions. However, variables such as corruption, agricultural production, exports, and urbanization boost emissions. This study shows the necessity of good governance and how the advent of renewable energy may minimize CO_2 emissions. Ali et al., (2021) evaluated the impacts of income, agricultural innovation, energy consumption, and biocapacity on carbon dioxide emissions in Nigeria from 1981 to 2014. By employing the ARDL modeling technique, the study reveals that agricultural innovation and energy usage lead to greater CO_2 emissions while increasing biocapacity and income levels assist reduce carbon emissions in the long term.

Chandio et al., (2020) examined the dynamic relationship between livestock output, crop production, energy consumption in agriculture, forest area and carbon dioxide emissions (CO_2) between 1990-2016 in China. Applying the automated distributed delay technique (ARDL) and Granger causality tests, study findings reveal that agricultural production and animal production have a beneficial influence on CO_2 emissions in both scenarios. However, energy consumption and forest areas have a negative influence on CO_2 emissions, lowering long-term CO_2 emissions. This study argues that boosting energy efficiency in agriculture and the growth of forest areas are efficient measures to minimize CO_2 emissions.

Edoja et al. (2016) studied the dynamic link among CO_2 emission (CE), agricultural productivity (AGP), and food security (FS) in Nigeria. The study employed yearly time series data from 1961-2010. The results from the Augmented Dicky and Fuller and Phillip Perron experiments applied analyzed how changes in CO_2 emissions effect agricultural production and food security. The findings from this study imply that a continual increase in CO_2 emissions would severely influence Agricultural production, hence posing a danger to food security. The authors believe that adopting sustainable agriculture techniques and minimizing CO_2 emissions will enhance food security in Nigeria.

The Guardian (2025) describes in an article how vertical agriculture is being utilized to conserve space and water and cut CO_2 emissions. An excellent case occurred when Wicks Far in the United Kingdom employed vertical agriculture to produce strawberries throughout the year, which led in a decrease in carbon emissions and the usage of water while enhancing performance. Regmi et al. (2024) employed the framework of the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) to examine the impacts of agricultural innovation, the use of renewable energy and economic growth on CO_2 Emissions in 1990 to 2018. Renewable energy use helps minimize long-term CO_2 emissions. Research reveals that supporting technical breakthroughs in agriculture and the development of renewable energy sources are viable measures to minimize CO_2 emissions.

Rafiq et al., (2016) explore the influence of the sector production allocation, energy consumption patterns and commercial opening in pollutant emissions in a panel comprising of high-, middle, and low-income nations. By employing three distinct heterogeneous dynamic panel models, the study demonstrates that agriculture added levels have a major role in lowering pollution levels, whereas industrialization raises pollution levels. It was determined from the data that the agricultural growth can enhance emissions, while the integration of global commercial networks can provide chances to embrace cleaner technology and practices, thereby minimizing environmental consequences. Khan et al. 2023 adopted the quantile regression to examine the EKC hypothesis to determine the relationships that exist between economic growth, agricultural productivity, and CO_2 emissions from 1991 to 2016. The results of this study show a negative relationship between economic growth and CO_2 emissions. In addition, agricultural productivity and CO_2 had negative relationships. The results of this research imply that policy formulators should consider the country's economic growth stage by lowering CO_2 emissions and conserving the environment, notably by restricting energy usage.

2.4. Existing Gaps in Literature.

The past research has offered diverse viewpoints on the importance of agriculture and energy in the reduction of CO_2 emissions in Nigeria and other nations. Most of the studies demonstrates a favorable association between agricultural, energy and CO_2 emissions {Dauda et al. (2023); Ali et al. (2021), Khan et al. (2023); Edoja et al. (2016)}, notably in Nigeria. This indicates that an increase in agriculture or energy leads to an increase in CO_2 emissions. Although various research has explored the link between agriculture, energy and CO_2 emissions, major gaps remain. Most empirical studies within Nigeria (Edoja et al., 2016; Ali et al., 2021) have focused on the direct relationship between agricultural productivity and carbon emissions without paying enough attention to the role of energy efficiency and technological advancement in reducing carbon footprint emissions. Despite the findings by Dauda et al. (2023) Highlighting the relevance of governance and policy frames to impact the level of agricultural energy emissions,

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international studies that compare developed and developing nations, there is less inquiry that deepens these conclusions, specifically for the unique economic and environmental situations of Nigeria. Empirical investigation on agricultural activities have resulted in divergent results with positive.

A notable gap in knowledge of empirical literature exploring the combined effects of agricultural and energy consumption on Nigerian CO_2 emissions is evident from the reviewed studies. Therefore, this research contributes to the existing body of knowledge by making insight on the effect of agricultural input and energy use on CO_2 emissions in Nigeria.

The extensive review of the literature has succinctly shown the existence of major gaps on the studies concerning the agriculture–energy–emissions nexus, especially in the Nigerian context. Most of these studies examine agriculture and energy in isolation, overlooked the mitigation role of sustainable agriculture, ignore technological and renewable energy transitions, and rely on outdated datasets (Talukder *et al.* 2021; Mensah *et al.* 2018; Ozcan & Strauss 2016; Zhang & Cheng 2009) Furthermore, few studies integrate macroeconomic variables such as urbanization and trade into a unified empirical framework or apply ARDL methodologies tailored to short-span but recent datasets. The interaction between agricultural sustainability, renewable energy adoption, and CO_2 emissions remain insufficiently explored.

3. METHODOLOGY

This research employs annual secondary time series data from 1990 to 2024. The data were procured from National Bureau of Statistics [NBS], Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA), International Energy Agency (IEA) and Central bank of Nigeria. The variables of the study are carbon dioxide emissions, agriculture and energy.

The agriculture–Environment Interaction theory will be adopted to explain the link between agricultural practices, energy consumption and carbon dioxide emissions. This theory is preferred because it recognizes agriculture as a direct relationship with carbon dioxide and energy usage. This theory argues that agriculture can either worsen or reduce environmental degradation depending on practices (Bulut, & Gökalp, 2022; Grossman & Krueger, 1995).

$$CO_2 = f(AGR) \dots\dots\dots(1).$$

CO_2 = carbon dioxide emission

$\theta_1 < 0$ -under sustainable/modern agriculture

$\theta_1 > 0$ \theta =under traditional agriculture

θ_1 = elasticity or marginal effect of agricultural activity on CO_2 emissions

The agriculture–Environment Interaction Theory does not originate from a single author; rather, it is a synthesized conceptual framework drawn from Boserup’s seminal 1965 work agricultural intensification model, ecological–economic linkages (Grossman & Krueger, 1995), and agro-ecological systems research (Tilman *et al.*, 2001; Pretty, 2008).

This research applies the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model to examine the impacts of energy consumption and agriculture on carbon dioxide (CO_2) emissions in Nigeria in the short and long run. The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model is selected for its robust performance, including effectiveness and reliability with limited data and its ability to capture both immediate and sustained relationships between variables.

The study aims to empirically determine the relationship that exist between agriculture, energy and CO_2 emissions, the study uses a multiple regression model that exemplifies related studies such as Shahbaz *et al.*, 2013; Odusanya *et al.*, 2020.

Therefore, the functional form of the model is;

$$CO_2 = f(agr, ene, gdp, trd, urb) \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

This model is formulated to capture the relationship between CO_2 emissions, agriculture and energy, as described by the following functional form:

$$CO_2 = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Agriculture + \beta_2 Energy Consumption + \beta_3 Gross Domestic Product Per Capita + \beta_4 Trade Openness + \beta_5 Urbanization Rate + \mu \text{ -----(2)}$$

Where β represents the level and the direction of the relationship that exist between each variable's effect on CO_2 and μ represents the error term that contains the other factors that affect CO_2 emissions but are not included in the model.

The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bounds testing approach was used to analyze the cointegration of variables, offering robustness in small samples and the ability to handle series with different integration orders {I(0) or I(1)}. This approach is favored because it allows for the simultaneous estimation of short and long run effects of agriculture and energy on CO_2 emissions in Nigeria even when their orders of integration differ. The error correction mechanism (ECM) is later applied to capture short-run dynamics.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Descriptive Analysis

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Study Variables

Measure	LCO ₂	AGR	LENE	LGDP	TOP	URB
Mean	18.37	24.24	5.71	7.22	3.35	4.45
Median	18.41	23.79	5.70	7.48	1.87	4.29
Maximum	18.72	36.97	5.93	8.04	20.79	5.57
Minimum	17.48	19.99	5.55	6.18	-3.70	3.51
Standard deviation	0.34	3.66	0.10	0.60	5.48	0.51
Skewness	-1.40	1.65	0.27	-0.56	1.36	-0.01
Kurtosis	4.27	6.36	2.10	1.81	4.69	2.28
Jarque-Bera	13.43	31.48	1.56	3.80	14.50	0.74
p value	.001	.000	.458	.150	.001	.691
Observations	34	34	34	34	34	34

Source: Author's Computation, 2025

The descriptive analysis result from Table 1 above revealed that the mean of LCO₂ is 18.37 with a standard deviation of 0.34. Similarly, AGR has a mean value of 24.24 with an S.D of 3.66. In the same vein, LENE recorded a mean of 5.71 and a relatively low S.D of 0.10. LGDP has a mean of 7.22 with a S.D of 0.60, while the average for TOP (trade openness) is 3.35 with a relatively high S.D of 5.48. The average value of URB (urbanization rate) stands at 4.45 with a S.D of 0.51. Beyond the above, the skewness statistics revealed that AGR, LENE, and TOP are positively skewed, while LCO₂, LGDP, and URB are negatively skewed. Furthermore, the Jarque-Bera test confirm that the residuals of LCO₂, AGR, and TOP significantly deviate from normality at the 1% level, while the distributions of LENE, LGDP, and URB conform to the normal distribution assumption.

Table 2: Unit Root Test Result

Variable	ADF statistic (Level)	t- PP statistic (Level)	t- p Value (Level)	Decision (Level)	ADF statistic (1st Diff.)	t- PP statistic (1st Diff.)	t- p Value (1st Diff.)	Decision (1st Diff.)
LCO ₂	-2.77	-2.77	.043	S	-6.45	-6.45	.000	S
LENE	-1.89	-1.89	.333	NS	-5.85	-5.85	.000	S
LRGDP	-1.86	-1.86	.348	NS	-4.91	-4.91	.000	S
TOP	-2.46	-2.46	.134	NS	-4.77	-4.77	.001	S
AGR	-1.92	-1.92	.319	NS	-6.49	-6.49	.000	S
URB	-1.89	-1.89	.333	NS	-8.47	-8.47	.000	S

Source: Authors’ Computation, 2025

The research employed a unit root test to confirm the stationarity characteristics of the variables. The integration analysis in table 2 demonstrates that the variables are I(0) and I(1), a condition that permits the application of the ARDL bounds test method. The unit root test results indicate that the variables are integrated of mixed orders I(0) and I(1) which has important implications for the methodological choices and the validity of the study’s results. This implies that the ARDL bound test for cointegration is valid and supports the estimation of both the long-run and short-run dynamics (Pesaran et al., 2001).

Table 3: Bounds Test for Cointegration Result

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t	P
D(LCO ₂)	-0.161	0.103	-1.56	.142
D(LNENE)	1.079	0.198	5.45	< .001
D(LNENE)	0.254	0.235	1.08	.301
D(LNENE)	-0.434	0.190	-2.29	.040
D(LGDP)	0.092	0.049	1.86	.085
D(TOP)	0.0001	0.006	0.01	.993
D(URB)	-0.040	0.124	-0.32	.755
D(URB)	-0.402	0.191	-2.10	.056
D(URB)	0.497	0.075	6.59	< .001
D(AGR)	-0.005	0.010	-0.48	.640
D(AGR)	-0.017	0.008	-2.09	.057
CointEq	-0.784	0.105	-7.48	< .001

Source: Author’s Computation, 2025

The estimates result from the short-run analysis indicates that current-period of log of energy consumption positively and significantly impacted CO₂ emissions with a coefficient of 1.079188 and a p-value of 0.0001 at 5% significance level. This supports the mitigation pathway of the agriculture–environment interaction theory. This implies that a one percent up rise in energy consumption yields 1.08% up rise in CO₂ emissions. Interestingly, the first lag of LENE (D(LENE(-1)) is insignificant (0.2537, p = 0.3008), while the second lag (D(LENE(-2)) is negatively significant at the 5% level with a coefficient of -0.433595 and a p-value of 0.0395. These mixed responses indicate that immediate energy consumption increases

environmental degradation, its lagged effects eventually reduce emissions, due to adaptation mechanisms, policy interventions, or shifts in energy efficiency.

Furthermore, the result revealed that economic growth (LGDP) and trade openness (TOP) were positive but insignificant in the short-run at 5% level of significance, meaning that the two variables do not exert any meaningful short-run influence on carbon-dioxide emissions.

Moreover, the effect of urbanization (D(URB) with time path exhibited a mixed results with an indication that the urban population contributes significantly to carbon-dioxide emissions in Nigeria. This is attributable to increased industrial activities, energy consumption, and transportation associated with expanding urban areas, a trend also noted by Adetayo and Aluko (2018) in their study on urban expansion and environmental stress in sub-Saharan Africa.

Similarly, both the current and lagged value of the agricultural sector (D(AGR) and D(AGR (-1) exhibited a negative impact but a minor statistically significant in the short run at 5% with a coefficient of -0.004614 and -0.017105 and a p-value of 0.6403 and 0.0566 respectively. This weak relationship suggests that agriculture, while land-intensive, is not a primary short-run contributor to emissions for the period under review, which can be attributable to the dominance of traditional farming practices that are less energy-intensive.

Table 4: ARDL BOUND TEST RESULT

Significance Level	I(0) Bound	I(1) Bound
10%	2.26	3.35
5%	2.62	3.79
2.5%	2.96	4.18
1%	3.41	4.68

Source: Authors' Computation, 2025

The ARDL Bounds testing approach was employed to verify a long-run relationship among CO₂ emissions, agriculture, and energy. A comparison of the Table 4 above with the critical values revealed that the F-statistic exceeds its upper and lower bound, a finding that confirms the presence of cointegration between the variables. The results demonstrate the ARDL model's effectiveness in capturing both long-run and short-run dynamics.

Table 5: ARDL Long-run Estimated Result

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t value	P value
LENE	1.255	0.288	4.37	.001
LGDP	0.038	0.072	0.53	.606
TOP	-0.007	0.006	-1.15	.273
URB	-0.159	0.051	-3.09	.009
AGR	-0.012	0.011	-1.12	.282
Constant	12.086	1.796	6.73	< .001

Source: Authors' Computation, 2025

The long-run estimates revealed that energy consumption (LENE) remains a key driver of emissions in the long run, with a positive and significant coefficient of 1.255401 and a p-value of 0.0008. This suggests that 1% yields in energy consumption is associated with a 1.26% up rise in CO₂ emissions over time. The persistent positive relationship reinforces the argument that the energy sector remains carbon-intensive, which is consistent with the findings of Sulaiman & Abdul-Rahim, (2017), who emphasized overdependence on fossil fuels in Nigeria.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Economic growth (LGDP) is found to have a positive but insignificant long-run relationship with emissions at 5% with a coefficient of 0.0379 and a p-value of 0.6057, reinforcing the earlier observation that GDP is not a key driver of the dependent variable within the studied period. Similarly, trade openness (TOP) exhibited a negative but insignificant impact on emissions at 5% with a coefficient of -0.00721 and a p-value of 0.2726. The result is consistent with the findings of Onakoya et al. (2013) who also found a positive and insignificant relationship between GDP and carbon emission.

Moreover, urbanization (URB) exhibited a negative and statistically significant impact on emissions at 5% with a coefficient of -0.1592 and a p-value of 0.0086. This outcome resonates with the conclusions of Okoye and Uchenna (2019) who suggested that urban renewal and investment in eco-friendly infrastructure can curb emissions in Nigerian cities.

Contrarily, agriculture (AGR) revealed a negative but insignificant relationship with CO₂ emissions at 5% with a coefficient of -0.0122 and a p-value of 0.2821. The model exhibits strong explanatory power with an R-squared of 0.9735 and an adjusted R-squared of 0.9389, indicating that the independent variables jointly explain over 90% of the variation in CO₂. This high goodness-of-fit reinforces the reliability of the model estimate.

Findings indicated that a significant inverse relationship between agricultural value-added and CO₂ emissions exist, which suggests that higher agricultural output is associated with lower long-term emissions. This is in corroboration with Binsuwadan et al., (2025) findings, but negate the outcomes of Ewah et al., (2020). As observed, higher energy consumption leads to a substantial and detrimental increase in CO₂ emissions, indicating that heavy reliance on fossil fuels degrades environmental quality. Also, the negative and statistically significant error correction term indicates that the system actively adjusts to restore the long-run balance, with the negative sign representing the direction of this adjustment.

In summary, the empirical data demonstrates agriculture's role in mitigating greenhouse gas emissions in Nigeria, whereas higher energy consumption worsens environmental harm and will continue to unless Nigeria migrates to renewable sources. These results corroborate the findings of Adegbulugbe (1991) and Ogunbiyi, (2020) emphasizing the necessity of integrating sustainable agriculture with renewable energy adoption.

5. CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

The agricultural sector (D(AGR)) exhibited a negative but statistically insignificant relationship with CO₂ emissions in the short-run. This weak relationship suggests that agriculture with land-intensive practices, is not a primary short-run contributor to emissions for the period under review, which can be attributable to the dominance of traditional farming practices that are less energy-intensive. This also supports the mitigation pathway of the agriculture–environment Interaction theory.

A negative and significant result was revealed from the error correction term, meaning there is a stable adjustment towards equilibrium. From these results, it is confirmed that agricultural development's role reduces environmental degradation while energy, currently heavily dependent on fossil fuels, will continually contribute to greenhouse gas emissions until

measures are taken to adopt and invest in renewable energy. As a consequence of the findings of this investigation,

Consequent upon the findings on the detrimental impact of fossil fuel energy consumption on CO_2 emissions, this study recommends that the Nigerian government shifts from non-renewable energy sources to renewable. This implies that the government should support the investment in renewable energy, such as solar, hydropower and wind facilities, and also establish laws that promotes the adoption of clean energy technology in the nation. This government may also offer subsidies or fiscal relief to renewable energy firms, supporting local manufacturing of renewable technology and guaranteeing that power is transported out to rural and isolated locations through renewable systems outside the network. which may assist in lowering carbon footprint.

Based on the findings that sustainable agricultural practices cut emissions, the government should support climate agricultural systems such as conservation agriculture, agroforestry and organic agriculture. And this may be done through the education of farmers, investments in agricultural research, subsidies for sustainable entrance and extension services. Robust policy frameworks and institutional resources should also be encouraged to execute environmental legislation successfully. Therefore, the Government must enhance the authorities that will supervise environmental management and guarantee robust monitoring, assessment and execution of climate-related policies in energy and agriculture sectors.

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